

KEY INDICATORS

With 56,810 hectares (2024), Slovenia had 11.7% of its farmland under organic management and was thus slightly above the EU average of 11.1%. Growth from 2001-2024 was almost tenfold and thus higher compared to most EU countries. Updated retail sales data is not available from Slovenia.

ORGANIC FARMLAND

2001

2024

Area* (Share of Total Farmland)

5,280 ha (1.1%)

56,810 ha (11.7%)

Area Growth from 2001 to 2024

976%

ORGANIC LAND USE & AQUACULTURE

2001

2024

Arable Land* (Share of Total)

N/D

8,618 ha (4.5%)

Permanent Crops* (Share of Total)

N/D

3,932 ha (13.8%)

Grassland* (Share of Total)

N/D

44,260 ha (15.8%)

Aquaculture Production (Share of Total)

N/D

610 t (36.4%) (2021)

ORGANIC OPERATORS

2001

2024

Producers (Share of Total)

883 (1%)

3,964 (5.5%)

Aquaculture Producers

N/D

4

Processors

N/D

233

Importers

N/D

16

ORGANIC RETAIL SALES

2001

2024

Retail Sales (Share of Total)

N/D

N/D

Per Capita Consumption

N/D

N/D

Imports

N/D

8,194 t

Source: FiBL survey based on national data sources, Eurostat and TRACES/European Commission in the framework of the OrganicTargets4EU project

*In conversion and fully organic

KEY INDICATORS

DEVELOPMENT OF ORGANIC FARMLAND IN SLOVENIA

Source: FiBL-AMI Survey, BMLRT, Nic Lampkin 2000-2023

CAP ORGANIC POLICY SUPPORT

The Slovenia CAP strategic plan provides for a 78% increase in supported organic area and expenditure by 2027 compared with 2018. To deliver this, and with almost all certified organic land supported, expenditure is forecast to grow by 132%, or on average per ha supported by 30%. Payment rates for arable and horticulture are set to increase by ca. 90% from 2023, and for vines and olives by ca. 30%, but the differential between conversion and maintenance payments will disappear. From 2025, organic farming has been prioritised for investment aids, processing and young farmers, with additional support for market development.

CONVERSION & MAINTENANCE

	2018	2027
Land Area Supported (Change from 2018)*	46 kha	82 kha (+78%)
Share of Total Agricultural Area Supported*	9.6 %	17% (+77%)
Share of Certified Organic Area Supported (Change)*	96%	N/D
Expenditure per Year*	10 M€	22 M€ (+132%)
Expenditure per Hectare Supported*	210 €	274 € (+30%)

SHARE OF CAP RESOURCES

CAP EXP. 2023-2027 ORGANIC SHARE*

Organic Farming Support (P2)*	93 M€	100%
Eco-Schemes (P1)	102 M€	
Agri-Environment, Climate, Welfare (P2)	329 M€	21.7%
Total CAP Expenditure	1,769 M€	5.3%

*including in-conversion and fully organic land

CAP ORGANIC CONVERSION AND MAINTENANCE PAYMENTS FOR DIFFERENT LAND USES

INDICATOR	YEAR	FUND	GRASSLAND	ARABLE CROPS	HORTICULTURE	FRUIT CROPS	GRAPES	OLIVES
Conversion Support (€/ha)	2019	P2	273	312	800	900	900	900
	2023	P2	159	607	1021	885	888	885
Change from 2019 to 2023			-42%	95%	89%	-2%	-2%	-2%
Maintenance Support (€/ha)	2019	P2	156	326	600	900	693	677
	2023	P2	159	607	1021	885	888	885
Change from 2019 to 2023			2%	86%	70%	-2%	28%	33%
Conversion Support Higher than Maintenance	2019	P2	75%	0%	33%	0%	30%	33%
	2023	P2	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%

P1 (Pillar 1) European Agricultural Guarantee Fund (EAGF); P2 (Pillar 2) European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD) and national co-financing

NATIONAL ORGANIC ACTION PLAN

Slovenia has had two organic action plans, the first dating back to 2005. The current plan sets a number of sub-targets for sector development with an emphasis on advice and training to achieve the goals, including a mandatory training programme for farmers with vouchers to enable farmers to obtain the training from alternative providers at reduced cost. From 2025, new targets have been set for advisory support (20% of Farm Advisory Service hours) and public procurement (15% in schools).

TARGETS

	PERIOD	LAND AREA TARGET	OTHER TARGETS
Previous Action Plan	2005-15	20% of UAA and farms by 2015	10% of market by 2015
Current Action Plan	2023-27	18% of UAA and 10% of farms by 2025	An increase in market above 1.8%

KEY ACTIONS

PREVIOUS ACTION PLAN (2005-2015)

CURRENT ACTION PLAN (2023-2027)

AQUACULTURE

The organic share of total aquaculture production in Slovenia in 2020 was 43%, the second highest national share in the EU, although both organic and conventional aquaculture are at low levels. Slovenia was not included in our analysis of the EMFF (2014-2020) and EMFAF (2021-2027) operational programmes and the Multi-annual National Strategic Plan for Aquaculture. As the funding is project specific and there is no ring-fenced organic budget, statistics on organic aquaculture support expenditure are not available.

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